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SCHOOL EDUCATION OF ADOLESCENTS DEPRIVED OF FREEDOM: BRAZILIAN REALITY AND LEGAL NOTION

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ABSTRACT

The right to education is defended within Brazilian legislation as a fundamental, social, public, subjective right and promoter of citizenship and human dignity. A right for all, education must be offered equally, observing the peculiarities of each case, as is the case of adolescents deprived of liberty who are serving socio-educational measures under the guardianship of the State. In this context, there is the legislative apparatus that guarantees their right and access to education, but the reality, in practice, is different. The present study aims to analyze the educational offer to adolescents deprived of their freedom, highlighting concepts related to the theme addressed, the legislative apparatus that currently deals with it and some data about it, in practice. For this, a qualitative research was used as a methodological procedure, in relation to the objective, it is an exploratory and descriptive research and on the research procedures, the study was characterized as bibliographic. The research was carried out in a virtual environment, in reliable databases such as Scielo, with scientific articles, monographs and thesis, with the descriptors: adolescents, Law, education, “socio-educational measure”, “private of liberty”. The resulting textual production is divided into two related titles, and the author’s impressions expressed in the final considerations as well as the conclusions.

Keywords: Teenagers. Right. Education. Private. Freedom. Socio-educational.